

The Effect Of Heat And Cold Waves On The Economic Costs Of Agricultural Production In Anbar Governorate

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: July 23, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: February 23, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Agricultural Production , Anbar Governorate</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6249945</p>	<p><i>The research aims to show the effect of heat and cold waves in increasing the economic costs on the agricultural crops under study in Anbar Governorate. This research came in order to show that every agricultural crop has climatic requirements, as every plant has minimum limits for the plant to grow or the so-called (zero growth), which is the degree at which the plant begins to grow, or the plant stops if it decreases to less than that, and this indicates that Every plant has a maximum temperature for growth, and if it exceeds that limit, the plant stops growing and different and effective damages occur as a result of exposure to heat waves.</i></p>

Introduction

Climate, with its elements and extreme phenomena, is at the forefront of natural factors that have a major impact on all stages of agricultural crop growth, from seeding to maturity. In this topic, we will address the effect of repeated heat and cold waves on the economic costs of agricultural production in terms of vegetable crops (field crops, vegetable crops, tuber crops (potatoes), fruit trees (apples, oranges) within the study area to see the extent of the impact of those waves, whether hot or cold .. cool in terms of quantity and quality.

Research problem

The research problem is one of the first steps of scientific research. The problem of the study is represented by the following question that pertains to the subject of the study, which is: Do heat waves have an impact on the economic costs of agricultural production in Anbar Governorate?

Research Hypothesis

The research hypothesis is represented by a main hypothesis centered around, as each research has a hypothesis and the hypothesis is a temporary solution to the problem, which basically represents the appropriate explanation for solving the main problem, and the research hypothesis goes to the effect of heat waves on agricultural crops.

Study area boundaries

The study area is defined spatially within the boundaries that include Anbar Governorate, which is one of the governorates of Iraq and the largest in area, as its total area is (138.501) km², which is approximately (31%) of Iraq, whose area is (438,317) km² located in its western section. The study area is geographically located between two latitudes (30.5° - 35°) North and (39° - 44°) East Longitude Map (1).

Map (1) the location of the study area

Source: The General Authority for Survey, the work of the researcher, based on the program

The first topic: the impact of heat waves on the economic costs of the crops under study

First: the monthly distribution of heat waves: The study area was exposed to a number of heat waves that reached (1485) throughout the period of the study, and the occurrence of heat waves in the study area varies between months of the year within its different stations, as July recorded the highest rate of heat waves, reaching (47.2) in the study area, followed by a month A monthly average of (46.8) heat waves in the study area, while the month of April recorded the lowest rate of heat waves (34.1) heat waves out of the total heat waves in the study area. As for the rest of the months, they recorded average heat waves that ranged between ((39-42.2 waves in each of the months (May, October) for each of them respectively. See the table () and the figure ().

Table (1) Monthly averages of heat waves by stations in Anbar Governorate for the period (1985-2018)

Months Stations	nisan	mays	hziran	tmuz	ab	aylul	tshrin1	almueadal
Rumade	34.9	43.1	45.2	48.9	47.2	44.6	39.9	43.4
Qeam	32.9	42.5	44.5	47.8	44.7	45.8	39.4	42.5

Hadith	34.7	41.5	46	46.3	46.2	44.7	40.1	42.8
Anae	33.2	44.1	44.6	45.4	49	43.1	38.2	42.5
Rutpa	33.8	39.2	42.5	47.1	45.2	43.5	36.7	41.1
Nukhaib	35.6	43.1	44.7	48.2	48.9	44.8	39.7	43.6
Average	34.1	42.2	44.5	47.2	46.8	44.4	39	-

Source: From the researcher's work based on the Ministry of Transport, the Iraqi General Authority for Meteorology and Seismic Monitoring, Climate Department, unpublished data, 2020.

Figure (1) Monthly averages of heat waves by stations in Anbar Governorate for the period(1985-2018)

Source: From the researcher's work based on Table (1)

Second: Heat waves and their impact on field crops.

Heat waves affect field crops on the physiological processes of the plant and affect the processes of rapid spread inside the plant of the nutrients that it absorbs and the process of photosynthesis. Heat waves affect all the stages the plant goes through and have a negative and dangerous impact if it happens to be repeated at the time of flowering because it destroys the fruit set and weakens Pollen and to study the effect of heat waves on field crops, we will study them, namely:

A – wheat

The wheat crop is one of the winter crops whose cultivation starts from November to (15 May) and it needs an optimum temperature (25°C). Any increase that reaches more than (38°C) leads to the death of the fetus and makes the plant irregular. Temperatures exceeding (40 C) or more lead to crop damage and damage to the crop. Crop damage and danger if it happened to rise at the time of flowering (1).

Heat waves lead to the vital weakness of pollen grains or lead to their death, and it leads to the lack of production of grains due to the lack of the fertilization process, and if the grains are formed, they will be atrophic, which leads to a decrease in quantity or damage to the crop, which negatively affects the farmer priest. The criticality of the wheat plant, as the increase in the frequency of heat waves leads to a weakening of the plant, a decrease in the number of spikes and damage to the crop.

Sometimes the wheat crop is exposed to heat waves that stop the growth of the grain and evaporate the water in it and negatively affect the crop. The increase in its frequency leads to an increase in the breathing process, and to an increase in the transpiration process, which increases the values of water consumption, leaving the plant gaps. It is open and the transpiration process increases when the temperature of the wave is more than (30 m) or more (2).

Then the plant spends an amount of water, which exposes it to permanent wilt and then death, especially when the soil is dry. The study was subject to heat waves in the months of April and May, bringing the average

temperature of the wave to (45 °C), while the maximum temperature that the crop can bear in the maturity stage is (32 °C), which is the maximum in the formation of spikes, while the temperature of the wave during the maturity stage was recorded (C). Table (1) looks at the study area in the maturity stage, which leads to the formation of small non-compliant grains. The maximum temperature that the crop can withstand, which sometimes reaches (49°C), which exceeds the maximum temperature that the crop can bear in the maturity stage, which is reflected in the quantity and quality of the crop.

B – barley

Heat waves affect the barley crop, the cultivation of which begins in the study area from October 15 to May 15, during the growing season. , as it bears the temperature that reaches (40 C) during the period of maturity, while the effect is when the temperature reaches (45 C) and for five consecutive days, its effect is clear on the damage of the spikes, especially in the maturity stage. It is known that each stage of growth The plant needs different temperatures, and the sowing date needs to be (20 m) in the month of October, but it goes around (38 m) as shown in Table (1) and the temperatures of the heat wave exceeded the maximum limits for the germination process, but the stage of maturity or the formation of spikes cannot bear

Table (2) The minimum, optimum, maximum and harmful temperature for the crops under stud

the crop	Minimum temperature Optimum	temperature Maximum	temperature Maximum	temperature Harmful
Wheat	4-5	29	37	40
barley	4-5	30	40	41
orange	12	25-15	30	44
apple	14	27-21	35	43
tomato	20	24-21	36	37
eggplant	18	27-21	36	40
spring potatoes	15	20-15	37	42
for autumn potatoes	15	20-15	37	42

Source: based on

1- Alia Muti Hamid Majed Al Yassin, Thermal efficiency and its relationship to the cultivation and production of wheat and rice in Iraq, Master's thesis (unpublished), College of Education for Girls, University of Kufa, 2009, p. 61.

2- Ahmed Taha Shihab al-Jubouri, Climate change and its impact on the productivity of some agricultural crops in Iraq, Master's thesis (unpublished), College of Arts, University of Baghdad, 1996, p. 51.

3- Nisreen Awad Abdoun, Spatial Relationships of Cultivation of Deciduous Fruit Trees with the Characteristics of the Iraqi Climate, Master Thesis, College of Education for Girls, University of Kufa, 2001, p. 23.

4- Qahtan Muhammad Hussain Al-Gawthari, The Impact of Climate on Planting Fruit Trees in Al-Qasim District, Master's Thesis, College of Arts, University of Al-Qadisiyah, 2016, p. 56.

Second: Heat waves and their impact on the cultivation and production of fruit trees

Heat waves are one of the most important elements that have an impact on many of the vital processes carried out by fruit trees in their different stages of growth, and each type or class of fruit has thermal requirements that it needs to complete its growth and when available it gives more production and better quality, and these requirements It has limits, and when those limits are available within the needs of fruit trees, it is considered ideal, and if it exceeds by a large degree to the extreme temperatures and for a long period, it is considered among the heat waves that have a significant impact on the production of agricultural crops and increase economic costs, whether by purchasing some medicines and pesticides to prevent heat waves Or by spoiling the crop. When heat waves persist for a long time, growth processes are hindered and production and may lead to the death and damage of fruit trees, or cause clear damage to them, and those damages depend on the length of the wave, whether it is short, medium or long, and the duration of its stay. It causes a decrease in the amount of crops produced (4). It can be divided into two parts.

A - evergreen fruit trees orange.

Heat waves are one of the climatic factors that affect the distribution, spread, production and growth of plants, as they affect the physiological and vital processes of plants in the process of photosynthesis, respiration, absorption of water and nutrients, and every physiological process carried out by the plant, which increases with increasing temperature until it reaches the optimum temperature and is Slow when it exceeds the permissible limit for the crop (5).

Evergreen fruit trees begin to grow and extend from the beginning of the month (March) to the end of the month (October). The maximum temperature reaches (38°C) and then growth begins to decline until it reaches a degree (49°C), and growth is almost non-existent when exposed to what is called (sunlight), in addition to the temperature rising for several consecutive days above the ability of the crop to withstand the maximum temperatures. Makes growth slow. This is evident in the study area through the image () and fruit trees differ in their tolerance of heat waves of all kinds, whether they are short, medium or long. Orange trees are the least tolerant of heat waves and are affected when temperatures reach (44-42 m) for a period of two days.

Table (3) The general average of area, production and productivity of agricultural crops for the period (1985-2018)

the crop	Cultivated area rate	productivity rate	productivity rate
Wheat	6497416	382.8	89176
Barley	28252	238.8	6414
Tomato	15072	4786.6	71711
autumn potatoes	17025	3186	54348
spring potato	19483	3525	86485
Orange	43702	17.6	7647
Apple	531654.8	13.7	7279.7

Source: Republic of Iraq, Ministry of Agriculture, Directorate of Agriculture in Anbar Governorate, Planning and Follow-up Department, unpublished data, 2020.

It has a great impact on the quantity and quality of production when it is accompanied by a decrease in relative humidity, as the increase in the frequency of heat waves leads to an increase in the fall of fruits and newly-developed flowers, which is what happens in the month of June or the so-called June fall (6). The increase in the frequency of heat waves in the study area in some years of the study had a noticeable impact on the quality and quantity of crops. The study area was exposed to heat waves that exceeded their average (m). The months (June, May, July, August) recorded temperatures of (44.4, 46.8, 47.2, 44.5 m) respectively, which is considered among the heat waves that have a significant impact on agricultural production (7). Therefore, the increasing frequency of heat waves is not appropriate with the different stages of agricultural production. In the flowering stage, it leads to killing

pollen and increasing flower fall, while in the stage of fruit formation

Picture (1) shows the orange crop of the heat wave

Source: the researcher based on the field study.

b- Apple deciduous fruit trees.

It is a well-known scientific fact that every agricultural crop has a minimum and maximum temperature. If it exceeds it, down or up, it will be destroyed. It is noted that the increase in the frequency of heat waves causes severe damage to those trees, starting with the roots, leaves, flowers and fruits (9).

The apple trees are of local varieties, they started to grow after the dormancy phase (resting phase) from the beginning of March to July 15 within the growing season. If the temperature is below this temperature, growth will stop.

From table (3), we note that the optimum temperature for apple trees ranges between (27-21 °C) and grow well, and this growth continues until it reaches the temperature ((36) and when it exceeds this

The degree of damage begins on the adult from the roots to the flowers, fruits and leaves, good commercial apple trees suffer great damage when the temperature exceeds 43 ((43). Fruits that are close to ripening and not homogeneous (10).

The fruits are exposed to damage when exposed to heat waves for more than three consecutive days, as it leads to tissue death, which appears in the form of small spots on the fruits facing the sun, and when the temperature is more than (37) and when it is accompanied by stillness of the wind for a period of one day, it turns color Brown with bad taste (11). It is clear from table (1) that the study area was exposed during the months (May and June July and August) to heat waves amounting to (42.2, 46.8, 47.2 m), which have an impact on the quantity and quality of production, so the cultivation of good quality apples in the study area does not succeed and depends on local varieties of low quality

Heat waves and their effect on vegetable crops in the study area 1-

Heat waves have a significant impact on the growth of green crops, and have a significant impact on the physiological processes of the plant, and their effect may vary according to the phase of the plant, starting from seed germination and its impact on the vegetative and fruitful growth of the plant (12).

That is, any increase in the recurrence of heat waves or high temperature that is not compatible with crops will lead to a defect in the productivity of vegetable crops and in the crop affected by the variables of climatic elements, whether they are summer or winter (13).

A number of row crops grow at optimum temperatures ranging from (27-21 °C), and their production is better and gives a good yield. The recurrence of heat waves in the summer that exceeds the ability of the crop during the months (June-July-August) in the study area, which exceeds the maximum temperature that it can withstand The crop that sometimes reaches (49 m) and rises to more than ((52) in some days of the maximum rates. By increasing the growth and accelerating the flowering of plants at an early age and exposing them to high temperatures and causing damage to the crop, and to the destruction of plant cells, reaching the point of death at which the active cells of most of the cells are destroyed Agricultural crops as a result of changes in the protoplasm of the cells of the plant itself (14). As for the level of pollen grains, their composition is abnormal or they die as a result of recurring heat waves that reduce the process of fertilization and fruit set, and sometimes lead to the death of the entire plant.

1-tomato

Tomato cultivation begins in the study area in the month of March to September. The optimum temperature for the tomato crop is from (24-21 °C), which is good for the yield of production, while high temperatures and recurring heat waves, which are more than (35), cause slower growth and damage to the crop. When the heat wave continues for more than four consecutive days, and the continuation of the growth season may lead to (36 m) for a long period exceeding the maximum temperature that the crop can bear to damage the crop. From May to September, it leads to flower drop and poor production and quality, and when the crop is exposed to hot waves, it leads to flower fall until the number becomes (3-2) flowers for each flower cluster out of (50)) flowers for each cluster (15). No recurrence of heat waves and an increase in the heat wave rate above the mentioned limit in the month of (March-May) it exceeded (38°C) causes the fruit-setting process to stop completely, pollen grains die, flowers and newly-set fruits fall off, crop damage and an increase in the economic cost of buying pesticides and plastic houses To protect the crop as a result of the crop losing water from plant tissues by the process of transpiration and depletion of manufactured carbohydrates as a result of the acceleration that occurs in the respiration process (16).

Heat waves and high temperatures have an effect on plant growth if it rises to (40 m) in the study area for several consecutive days, because it leads to the formation of male flowers more than female, which causes a significant decrease in the rate of occurrence in the summer and the increase in the frequency of heat waves causes death (%) 20 pollen grains, and when the temperature of the wave rises to (43 °C), the process of pollination of tomatoes is negatively affected, so only (65%) of the flowers are pollinated due to the slow pollen tube caused by the high heat wave (17). In the long heat, white spots appear on it, which causes a deficiency inside it and the surface of the white spot rots inside it, and the picture (2) illustrates this.

Many studies have proven that the temperature rise and the recurrence of heat waves have a significant impact on agricultural crops when they exceed (35°C) at the time of maturity. The crop is between June and August, which in turn leads to crop damage. When comparing the climatic requirements of the tomato crop, we note that it exceeds the harmful temperature of the crop, which affects the quantity and quality of the crop and productivity, and this explains the interruption of the tomato crop in the hot months because this negatively affects the crop and has a negative impact on the farms .

Picture (2) shows the tomato crop in a heat wave

Source: the researcher with the accreditation of the field study.

2- eggplant

The cultivation of the eggplant crop in the study area starts from the month (March) to the month (September) the length of the growing season and that the optimum temperatures for the growth of the crop range between ((27-21), which is good in production, but the eggplant crop is affected when the temperatures rise above the temperature The maximum tolerance of the crop is when it exceeds (35 m) during the flowering period and affects pollen grains, which reduces the fertilization process for eggplant fruits (18).The eggplant crop is often damaged when the time of flowering coincides with the time of high temperatures and frequent heat waves in the study area in The months of July and August, in which the wave average exceeds (45 °C), and this is what happens to the late species (Afli), which coincides with the time of its flowering with high and frequent high temperatures that exceed the maximum temperature that the crop can bear, and it falls The flowering of the crop is not complex. It is clear from the table () that the rate of heat waves exceeded the harmful high temperatures that the crop can bear for the crop, which causes the fruits to wilt as in the picture (2). As a result of the repetition of high heat waves that negatively affect the crop and low humidity that cannot be compensated by water, which results in a lot of transpiration that causes a lack of water in the plant tissues and then the fall of the fruits despite the availability of water in the soil due to the weakness of the root group.

The picture (3) shows the eggplant crop in a heat wave

Source: the researcher with the accreditation of the field study.

A- Effect of heat waves on potato tuber crops (spring and autumn).

The effect of heat waves on the spring and autumn potato crop has an impact on the crop and at the two peaks, whether during its growth stages or during the harvest, which has an impact on the crop, as exposure of the crop to heat waves leads to crop damage, as autumn potato cultivation thrives at a temperature ranging from (20- 20). 15° C), while the average wave temperature for some months (June, July, August) was higher than the maximum temperature that the crop can bear, and this in turn exposes the crop to damage and also affects the quantity, quality and productivity of the crop (19). The formation of tubers decreases if the average temperature of the heat wave rises above (38 °C), and its formation stops when exposed to heat waves in which the temperature of the wave increases.

1. Prices of the factors of production: the costs increase as the prices of the factors of production used in production rise.
2. Efficiency in the use of production factors: costs decrease with increasing efficiency in the use of production factors.
3. Technology used: where technological progress allows the production of more of a particular commodity using the same amount of inputs, or the production of the same quantity with fewer inputs (20).

Types of production costs

Costs can be divided into several types depending on the angle from which these costs are viewed. Accountants are usually concerned with the apparent costs, which are the sum of money incurred by the producer in exchange for services on the services of the factors of production that he used in production and which he is unable to obtain without paying for them.

It includes the wages of the workers, the prices of raw materials, the prices of the consumed energy, the transportation services, insurance, the interest paid on the capital, the rent paid for renting the project land, and the value of the depreciation of the machines and machines used in production. It also includes the normal profit of the organizer. In a word; Just as the process of “paying” entails, in addition to this type of costs, there are the implicit costs Which do not appear in the form of apparent payments, such as the costs of using the inputs owned by the product itself, such as his personal effort and capital, the existence of this type of costs is what makes it possible to differentiate between economic profit and accounting profit, accountants usually neglect this type of costs because they do not appear in the books The accounts are due to the lack of a payment process for them. As for the economist, he looks at the activity of the organizer as an element of cost, because the organization is an element of the contemporary production, that is, the costs include the pr First: Fixed Costs:

They are the costs borne by the producer regardless of the volume of production, that is, the fixed costs are independent of the output and will be borne by the producer even if it stops production. In other words, it is the cost incurred by the project during the year, whether it is produced or not, for example, seeds and fertilizers, the rent of machinery and equipment or the cost of Purchase it or insurance premiums, fixed tax and depreciation of

machinery and equipment. In general, it should be noted that the above costs, if they take the form of equal or unequal payments and for a specific period with the output, are counted among the variable costs and not the fixed ones, just as all costs (even fixed) become variable in the long term (2).

ofit of the organizer, which is called the normal profit. The costs can be classified into:

Table (4) Fixed economic costs of agricultural crops under study

the crop	Wheat	Barley	tomato	Eggplant	autumn potatoes	spring potato	Orange	apple
seeding cost	120.000	100.000	70.000	50.000	500.000	500.000	0	0.
Fertilizer cost	125.000	125.000	150.000	150.000	150.000	150.000	100.000	100.000
Plowing, softening and opening my stems	60.000	60.000	65.000	65.000	75.000	75.000	50.000	50.000
fuel cost	35.000	30.000	40.000	10.000	15.000	15.000	10.000	10.000
cost of rented labor	50.000	30.000	80.000	50.000	50.000	50.000.	45.000	45.000
harvest cost	55.000	50.000	55.000	55.000	40.000	40.000	135.000	135.000
irrigation cost	60.000	60.000	75.000	60.000	60.000	60.000	45.000	45.000
animal manure	10.000	10.000	25.000	15.000	15.000	15.000	25.000	25.000
Transfer and upload	45.000	40.000	35.000	20.000	50.000	50.000	10.000	10.000
Other costs	15.000	15.000	5.000	5.000	15.000	15.000	5.000	5.000
Total	575.000	520.000	60.000	480.000	970.000	970.000	425.000	425.000
production acres/ton	4.000	3.000	4.000	3.000	5.000	5.000	3.000	3.000
price per ton	500	400	350000	750.000	450.000	450.000	900.000	500.000
Costs	2575000	1720000	1800000	2730000	2770000	2770000	3128000	1925000
The ratio %	13.2	9	9.2	14.1	14.2	14.2	16.1	10

Source: 1- Ministry of Agriculture, Director of Agriculture in Anbar Governorate, Central Bureau of Statistics, unpublished data for the year 2020. 2- Field study.

1- field crops

It is clear from the table that the study of the fixed costs of crops to highlight the importance of each type of costs, as the table shows that the costs of producing one acre of wheat crop vary between each paragraph of the production requirements from seed to marketing of the crop, where the costs of producing one acre of wheat crop reached (2,575,000) thousand dinars per acre, with a percentage of (13.2%) of the total economic costs of the crops under study, while the economic costs of the barley crop, which is one of the winter crops in which the impact of heat and cold waves on the crop is less than the rest of the crops, where the fixed costs of the crop were (1,720,000) thousand per dunam, with a percentage of (9%).

1- vegetable crops

It is clear from the table () that the fixed costs of a crop for the production of a dunum one, with a percentage of (13.2%) of the total economic costs of the crops under study, while the economic costs of the barley crop, which is one of the winter crops in which the impact of heat and cold waves on the crop is less than the rest of the crops, where the fixed costs of the crop amounted to (1,720000) thousand per dunam, with a percentage of (9%).

1- vegetable crops

It is clear from the table () that the fixed costs of a crop for the production of one acre of tomato amounted to (1,800,000) thousand dinars per acre, with a percentage of (9.2%), while the fixed costs of the eggplant crop per acre amounted to (2730000) thousand dinars, with a percentage of (14.1).), from the total economic costs of the crops under study.

2- Tuberous crops

It is clear from the table () that the fixed costs of producing one acre of potatoes in the two crops

The spring and autumn amounted to (2,770,000) thousand dinars, or a percentage of (14.2), of the total fixed costs of the crops under study.

3- Fruit crops

It is clear from the table () that the fixed costs of producing one acre of the orange crop amounted to (3128000) thousand dinars, with a percentage of (16.1%), while the fixed costs of producing one acre of the apple crop were (1925000), with a percentage of (10%). Of the total costs of agricultural crops under study.

Second: variable costs:

It is defined as the cost of the variable production elements necessary for the production of agricultural crops, which is the part of the costs in the short period that change with the change in the volume of production of the crops under study. That the size of the project changes, so it is an increasing function of the volume of production, and this cost includes wages of workers, seeds, fertilizers and plowing, the value of raw materials for water pumps in addition to the pesticides used to avoid the crop from losses, electricity and water costs, marketing and transportation costs, maintenance expenses (22) , ...etc.

Table (5) Variable economic costs of agricultural production in Anbar Governorate

the crop	Wheat	barley	tomato	Eggplant	autumn potatoes	spring potato	Orange	apple
seeding cost	120.000	110.000	70.000	50.000	500.000	500.000	0	0
Fertilizer cost	210.000	210.000	175.000	175.000	175.000	175.000	100.000	100.000
Plowing, softening and opening my stems	60.000	60.000	65.000	65.000	75.000	75.000	50.000	50.000
fuel cost	35.000	30.000	40.000	10.000	15.000	15.000	10.000	10.000
cost of rented labor	50.000	30.000	80.000	50.000	50.000	50.000	45.000	45.000
harvest cost	55.000	55.000	75.000	75.000	40.000	40.000	135.000	135.000
irrigation cost	60.000	60.000	75.000	60.000	60.000	60.000	45.000	45.000
animal manure	10.000	10.000	125.000	90.000	15000	15.000	25.000	25.000
Transfer and upload	45.000	40.000	35.000	20.000	50.000	50.000	10.000	10.000
Other costs	15.000	15.000	5.000	5.000	15000	15.000	5.000	5.000
Total	125.000	125.000	125.000	75.000	80.000	80.000	25.000	25.000
production acres/ton	785.000	745.000	870.000	675.000	1075000	1075.000	450.000	450.000
price per ton	3850	2900	2950	2900	4900	4900	2900	300
Costs	500.000	400.000	350.000	750.000	450.000	450.000	900.000	500.000
The ratio %	2710000	1910000	1902000	2850000	3209000	3209000	3150000	1950000
seeding cost	12.9	9.1	9.1	14	15.3	15.3	15	9.3

Source: 1- Ministry of Agriculture, Director of Agriculture in Anbar Governorate, Central Bureau of Statistics, unpublished data for the year 2020. 2- Field study

1- field crops

It is clear from the table that the study of the variable costs of crops to highlight the importance of each type of costs, as the table shows that the production costs of one dunum for each crop were taken in disparity between each paragraph of the production requirements from seed to marketing of the crop, where the production costs of one dunum of wheat crop reached (2710,000) A thousand dinars per acre, with a percentage of (12.9%) of the total economic costs of the crops under study, where the fertilizer costs for the two crops took (210,000) thousand dinars, while the variable costs were (125,000) dinars, while the costs of activating and adding stimulants amounted to (125,000)) dinars, while the fixed amount was (15000) dinars, and these requirements were taken higher than they were in fixed costs, they added that productivity took a decline due to heat and cold

waves on the crop, While the economic costs of the barley crop, which is considered one of the winter crops in which the impact of heat and cold waves on the crop is less than the rest of the crops, where the variable costs of the crop amounted to (1910000) thousand per dunum, with a percentage of (9.1%).

2- Vegetable crops

It is clear from the table () that the variable costs of the crop for the production of one acre of tomato amounted to (1902000) thousand dinars per acre, with a percentage of (9.2%). Or in the years that are free of heat and cold waves, as the fertilizer costs amounted to (175,000) thousand dinars for the crops than it was in the fixed costs, which amounted to (125,000) thousand dinars, with an estimated difference between the two types of costs (50,000) thousand dinars per acre. As for the costs that pertain to Animal fertilizer amounted to (125,000) thousand dinars per acre for tomato crop, while the fixed costs of animal fertilizer were(25,000) thousand dinars per acre, and a difference between the two types of costs (100,000) thousand dinars, while the variable costs of the eggplant crop per acre amounted to (2,850,000) thousand dinars, with a percentage of (14%), of the total economic costs of the crops under study. As for the animal manure for the eggplant crop, it was estimated at (90,000) thousand dinars, while it was estimated in the year that was free of heat and cold waves at (15000) thousand dinars, while the costs of stimulants recorded the highest amount of fixed costs, which amounted to (125,000) thousand dinars for the tomato crop. As for the costs of stimulants for the eggplant crop, it amounted to (75,000) thousand dinars, and this increase in production requirements and a decrease in the productivity of a dunum will be reflected in an increase in the cost of producing large areas.

3- Tuberous crops

It is clear from the table () that the variable costs of the crop for the production of one acre of potatoes in Al-Urutin amounted to (3209,000) thousand dinars per dunam, with a percentage of (15.3%). Fixed costs or in years that are free of heat and cold waves, as the fertilizer costs amounted to (175,000) thousand dinars for the crops than it was in the fixed costs, which amounted to (150,000) thousand dinars, with an estimated difference between the two types of costs (25,000) thousand dinars per acre. As for the costs that Concerning animal manure, it amounted to (50,000) thousand dinars per acre for the potato crop, while the fixed costs of animal fertilizer amounted to (15,000) thousand dinars per acre. The fixed costs of animal manure (15,000) thousand dinars per acre, while the costs of steroids recorded the highest amount of fixed costs, amounting to (80,000) thousand dinars for the potato crop.

4- Fruit trees

It is clear from the table () that the variable costs of producing one acre of the orange crop amounted to (3,150,000) thousand dinars, and a percentage amounted to ((15%), while the fixed costs of the orange crop were (128000) and a percentage amounted to (16.1%), while the variable costs were (1950000) for the production of one dunum of the apple crop, while the fixed costs of producing one dunum of apples were (1925000), with a percentage of (10%) of the total costs of the agricultural crops under study.

Results

The study showed in the light of reality the heat and cold waves and their impact on the economic costs of production and the crops that are grown in grain and vegetables according to the scientific method that was studied and the methods and means through which it is possible to analyze the impact of heat and cold waves in increasing the economic costs of production. The study reached a number of conclusions It can be inserted in Plat:-

1. The study area owns a geographical location and has arable land.
2. The results of the study showed that heat waves that start with the gradual rise in temperatures have an impact on the economic costs of agricultural production in the governorate, as most crops are affected by heat waves in which temperatures exceed the permissible limit for most of the crops under study.
3. The study showed that the highest rate of heat waves was recorded in the wailing station, which reached (43.6), followed by the Ramadi station, with a rate of (43.4).
4. The study showed that the highest rate of heat waves was recorded in the month of (May, August) at a rate of (46.8 48.2).
5. The study showed that there was a big difference between the fixed costs and the variable costs in the impact of heat waves, as the study showed that most of the costs spent on agricultural crops increased more than they were in the years that were free of heat waves.

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